

**Job satisfaction and organisational commitment:
An Empirical Evidence in Small and Medium Size Enterprises in
Cameroon.**

**Satisfaction au travail et engagement organisationnel:
Une étude empirique dans les petites et moyennes entreprises au
Cameroun.**

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of job satisfaction on the commitment of employees of small and medium size enterprises (SMEs) in Cameroon for their organisations. General job satisfaction was used as dependent variable then the three foci of commitment were used as dependent variables. Three hypotheses were formulated based on the link of the concepts in literature. The data for the study was collected using questionnaire on a sample size of 1556 employees of SMEs in Cameroon. The data was analysed using Pearson correlation analyses and regression analyses.

The result reveals that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the affective, normative and continuance commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisations. From this result it was recommended that the management of SMEs in Cameroon should always bring up strategies to keep their employees satisfied to their jobs so as to be committed.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction; Affective commitment; Normative commitment; Continuance commitment.

Résumé

L'objectif principal de cette étude était d'étudier l'influence de la satisfaction au travail sur l'engagement des salariés des petites et moyennes entreprises (PME) au Cameroun. La satisfaction générale au travail a été utilisée comme variable dépendante, puis les trois variables de l'engagement selon Allen et Meyer ont été utilisées comme variables dépendantes. Trois hypothèses ont été formulées à partir du lien des concepts dans la littérature. Les données de l'étude ont été recueillies à l'aide d'un questionnaire sur un échantillon de 1556 employés de PME au Cameroun. Les données ont été analysées à l'aide d'analyses de corrélation de Pearson et d'analyses de régression. Le résultat révèle que la satisfaction au travail a une influence positive et significative sur l'engagement affectif, normatif et de continue des salariés des PME. À partir de ce résultat, il a été recommandé que la direction des PME camerounaises élabore toujours des stratégies afin de maintenir leurs employés satisfaits de leur travail afin de s'engager.

Mots clés: Satisfaction au travail; engagement affectif; engagement normatif; engagement de continue.

Introduction

As the development level of a nation increases, the working environment becomes more competitive. Thus keeping employees becomes primordial, we can therefore underline that the human dimension is a source of competitive advantages and also the ability of an organization to retain and motivate this human dimension is a critical variable contributing to the success of the organization (Ouassal, 2020). Employers now seek for additional skilled, well trained and qualified employees since the organisational output highly depends on these employees' performances (Currall et al., 2005). These qualified employees therefore seek for more good looking pay packages, and to maintain performance has always been the target for the human resource management practitioners (Rai Sumita, 2004).

In 1976, Locke and Lathan gave an understandable definition of job satisfaction as pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of one's job or job tenure. Job satisfaction results from employee's view of how well their job gives those things that are seen as crucial. According to Mitchell and Lasan (1987), it is widely recognised in the field of organisational behaviour that job satisfaction is the most crucial and frequently studied attitude. The reason why when employees are satisfied it will lead to commitment is that a higher level of job satisfaction can lead to good work life and decrease in stress (Cote & Heslin, 2003).

Commitment is a construct that explain consistencies involving attitudes, beliefs and behaviour and includes behavioural choices and implies a rejection of possible different courses of action (Hulin, 1991). Organisational commitment has been seen widely in terms of its correlates, components, antecedents, and consequences (Mathieu and Zajac, 1990). Meyer and Allen (1997) brought out three elements of organisational commitment which are; affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Affective commitment is the extent to which a person identifies with his/her organisation (identification, involvement, and emotional attachment). Normative commitment shows the extent to which a worker believes he/she is being committed to his/her organisation and may be influenced by the norms of the organisation. Continuance commitment describes a person's desire to keep working for his/her organisation based on the perceived costs tied with leaving (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Meyer and Allen, 1991, 1997).

Throughout this paper we will be bringing out the realities of job satisfaction and organisation commitment of employees of SMEs in Cameroon, that is, to see if job satisfaction has an influence on the level of the commitment employees of SMEs in Cameroon have for their

organisation. For these to be achieved, we will present a review of literature, problem of statement, methodology and then present the findings of the study with some policy recommendations.

1. Literature review

1.1 Job satisfaction

The concept of motivation is often linked with job satisfaction and theories of motivation have often formed the basis and models and measures of job satisfaction (Mullins 1996). Although job satisfaction is not synonymous with motivation it could be associated with a personal feeling of achievement. Motivation is a process which may link to job satisfaction. It is from this background that we ought to present some predominant theories of job satisfaction, having in mind that most theories of motivation are closely related to job satisfaction.

Porter/Lawler Expectancy Model (1968): This model is a very popular explanation of the job satisfaction process. Porter and Lawler stress that ‘effort’ (force or strength of motivation) does not lead directly to ‘performance.’ It is rather moderated by the ‘abilities and traits’ and the ‘role perceptions’ of an employee. Furthermore, ‘satisfaction’ is not dependent on performance rather determined by the ‘probability of receiving fair rewards’ (Wehrich & Koontz, 1999). The Porter-Lawler model suggests that motivation is affected by several interrelated cognitive factors, such as motivation results from the ‘perceived effort-reward probability.’ However, before this effort is translated into performance, the ‘abilities and traits’ and ‘role-perceptions’ of employee has an effect on the efforts used for performance. Furthermore, it is the ‘perceived equitable rewards’, which determine ‘job-satisfaction’ of the workforce (Luthans, 2005). Value-Percept Theory: Locke (1976) argued that individuals' values would determine what satisfied them on the job. Only the unfulfilled job values that were important to the individual would be dissatisfying. According to Locke's value-percept model, job satisfaction can be modelled by the formula below;

$$S = (V_t - P) \times V_i$$

Or

$$\text{Satisfaction} = (\text{want} - \text{have}) \times \text{importance}$$

Where S is satisfaction, V_t is value content (amount wanted), P is the perceived amount of the value provided by the job, and V_i is the importance of the value to the individual. Thus, value-percept theory predicts that discrepancies between what is desired and what is received are dissatisfying only if the job facet is important to the individual. Because individuals consider

multiple facets when evaluating their job satisfaction, the cognitive calculus is repeated for each job facet. Overall satisfaction is estimated by aggregating across all contents of a job, weighted by their importance to the individual.

Affective Event Theory: According to Thompson & Phua (2001) the affective event theory was developed by Psychologist Howard and Russell to explain how emotions and moods influence job satisfaction. The theory explains the linkages between employees' internal influences; cognitions, emotions, mental states etc and their reactions to incidents that occur in their work environment that affect their performance, organisational commitment, and job satisfaction (Wegge, Van Dick, Fisher, West & Dawson, 2006). The theory further proposes that affective work behaviours are explained by employees' mood and emotions, while cognitive-based behaviours are the best predictors of job satisfaction

1.2 Commitment

To better understand the current state of commitment research, a description of the development of the concept and measurement of OC and the way they have affected current conceptualisations of commitment is needed.

The first contemporary theory of organisational commitment was the "side-bet" theory put forward by Becker in 1960. According to this theory, committed employees are committed because they have totally hidden or somewhat hidden investment, "side bet", they have made remaining in a given organisation. Becker (1960) concentrated on what he termed "side-bets" which attempted to explain the process to which employees attach themselves to organisations through investment such as time, effort and reward. These investments however have cost which reduce to some degree on employee's freedom in his or her future activity. Through investment employees get locked into organisations because of costs associated with leaving the organisation (for example, pension plans, seniority and firm specific knowledge) (Claire, 2004).

Second period of organisational commitment was advanced by Porter et al. in 1974 (Affective-dependence period or the psychological attachment approach). The focus of commitment shifted from tangible side-bets to the psychological attachment one had to the organisation. The attitudinal approach advanced by Porter and his colleagues attempted to describe commitment as a focused attitude, uncontaminated by other constructs such as behavioural intentions. Accordingly, commitment was defined by Porter and his followers as "...the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organisation..." (Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979). Commitment here was characterised by

three related factors:“(1) a strong belief in and acceptance of the organisation's goals and values; (2) a willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organisation; and (3) a strong desire to maintain membership in the organisation...”The exchange theory was established as the main explanation for the process of commitment (Mowday, Porter and Steers, 1982).

Becker (1960) and Porter (1974) theories belonged all to the one-dimension era, after them, two leading multidimensional approaches were advanced in the 1980s, one from O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) and the other from Meyer and Allen (1984). There were some other multidimensional approaches, but these had much less impact than the two main ones (Herscovitch and Mayer, 2002).

The way the individual is attached to the organisation was profoundly investigated by Etzioni (1961) as well (organisational commitment as moral, calculative, and alienative attachment). It was on the basis of his work that Penley and Gould (1988) created a commitment model consisting of three components. The three dimensions of commitment identified here are moral, calculative, and alienative commitments. Moral commitment is based on an acceptance of and or identification with organisational goals. Calculative commitment is based on the employee's receiving inducements to match his contributions. Alienative commitment results when the individual no longer receives compensations commensurate with his efforts, and yet he remains. Causes of staying are to be searched among external circumstances: lack of alternative job options, potential considerable financial loss resulting from quitting, and so on. O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) build their approach upon what they portrayed as the problematic state of commitment research, namely the failure to differentiate carefully among the antecedents and consequences of commitment on the one hand, and the basis for attachment on the other. They defined commitment as the psychological attachment felt by a person for his organisation, reflecting the degree to which the individual internalises or adopts the characteristics or perspectives of the organisation. They argued that one's psychological attachment may be predicted by three independent factors:

- ✓ compliance or instrumental involvement for specific, extrinsic rewards
- ✓ identification or involvement based on a desire for affiliation
- ✓ internalisation or involvement predicated on the congruence between individual and organisational values

Allen and Meyer defined organisational commitment as “a psychological link between the employee and his or her organisation that makes it less likely that the employee will

voluntarily leave the organisation (Allen and Meyer 1990). Allen and Meyer first identified two dimension of organisational commitment; affective attachment and cost attachment. After continued research, Meyer and Allen identified another dimension which was obligation.

The three distinct components of organisational commitment identified by Meyer and Allen were termed affective orientation or affective commitment, cost-based orientation or continuance commitment, obligation (moral), responsibility or normative commitment.

Affective commitment; The affective component of organisational commitment refers to an employee continuing to work for an organisation because of the employee's emotional attachment to, involvement in and identification with that organisation (Allen and Meyer 1990). For example, one can feel proud to be a member of organisation X and truly want X to be successful. Employees with a strong affective commitment continue with an organisation because they want to.

Continuance commitment; Continuance commitment refers to the commitment that is based on the cost that is associated with leaving a specific organisation. The potential cost of leaving an organisation includes threats of wasting time and effort spent acquiring non-transferable skills, losing attractive benefits, giving up seniority based privileges or having to up root family and disrupt personal relationship. Employees whose primary link to the organisation is based on continuance commitment remain because they need to.

Normative commitment; Normative commitment refers to the employee's perceived obligation to remain with their organisation or reflect the feeling of obligation to continue employment in an organisation. Wiener (1982) suggested that the feeling of obligation to remain with an organisation might result from internalisation or normative pressure exerted on an individual prior entry into the organisation (family, cultural orientation) or following entry (organisational orientation). Normative commitment might also develop when an organisation provides the employee with "reward in advance" (paying college tuition) or incur significant cost in providing employment (cost associated with job training). Employees with high level of normative commitment feel that they ought to remain with the organisation.

1.3 Job satisfaction and commitment

Spector (1997) states that job satisfaction influences people's attitude towards their jobs and various aspects of their jobs. Job satisfaction is affected by personal and organisational factors, which cause an emotional reaction which is tied to the affective construct of organisational commitment (Mowday, Steers & Porter 1979). The consequences of job satisfaction include better performance and a reduction in withdrawal and counter-productive

behaviours (Morrison 2008). Since job satisfaction involves employees' affect or emotions, it influences an organisation's well-being with regard to job productivity, employee turnover, absenteeism and life satisfaction (Sempane, Rieger & Roodt, 2002; Spector 2008).

The concept of Job Satisfactions has been widely discussed by various researchers. The most popular definition was provided by Locke (1976), where Job Satisfaction is simply a positive emotional state of feeling resulted from jobs, thus fulfil individuals' value towards their jobs. This definition further suggests that job satisfaction contains an affective component (emotional state) and cognitive component (appraisal) of Job Satisfaction (Organ & Konovsky, 1989). Affective Job Satisfaction states the individual's immediate feeling state towards job-related factors. It is the extent of pleasurable emotional feelings individuals have about their jobs overall. The positive emotion of feelings may include feeling good about the job, individual being delegated, and the particular feeling is experienced from their appraised work performance, recognised professions, and even completion of work task (Megginson et. al., 1982). The definition of job satisfaction by Locke (1976) talks of a pleasurable emotional feeling of an individual about his/her job which is tied with the definition of affective commitment by Allen and Meyer (1990) who defined affective commitment as employees' emotional attachment to, identification with and involvement to an organisation. On the other hand, the Cognitive Job Satisfaction is tied to the expectations and standards of comparison in terms of which current circumstances are being evaluated. It is the extent of individuals' satisfaction with particular facets or aspects of their jobs.

Hoppock defined job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job (Hoppock, 1935). According to this approach, although job satisfaction is under the influence of many external factors, it remains something internal that has to do with the way and how the employee feels. That is job satisfaction presents a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction. Vroom in his definition on job satisfaction focuses on the role of the employee in the workplace. Thus he defines job satisfaction as affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying (Vroom, 1964). Organisational commitment is defined in terms of the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organisation (Mowday, Steers, & Porter, 1979). Basically, organisational commitment is considered to be a bond linking the individual to the organisation (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990). A perusal of the extant literature indicates that in

a majority of these studies, organisational commitment has been viewed as a general affective response of an employee to the organisation as a whole. In other words, this form of commitment is referred to as affective commitment (Aizzat, et al., 2015).

Salancik (1977) explained the behavioural approach to commitment wherein overt manifestations of commitment are shown representing sunk costs in the organisation where individuals forego alternative courses of action and chose to link themselves to the organisation. Behavioural commitment relates to the process by which individuals become locked into an organisation and how they deal with the problem. Marsh and Mannari (1977) found that the committed employee considers it morally right to stay in the company, regardless of how much status enhancement or satisfaction the firm gives him over the years. Wiener and Gechman (1977) opined that commitment behaviours are socially accepted behaviours that exceed formal and/or normative expectations relevant to the object of commitment. The part of satisfaction linked to normative commitment is the socialisation process of the individual or employee to his/her organisation and becomes satisfied with what the organisation has done for him over a period of time and then decides to be loyal to his organisation, which becomes some sought of pay back to the organisation.

Job satisfaction is typically construed (examined) either as an affective or emotional attitude of an individual towards his or her job (James & Jones, 1979) or as a general attitude towards a job and some particular aspects of it (Knoop, 1995). We take the position that job satisfaction has two facets relating to the extrinsic and intrinsic features of a job (Cooper-Hakim & Viswesvaran, 2005), a formulation that can be traced back to Herzberg (1968). Extrinsic job satisfaction relates to satisfaction from, for example, pay, physical conditions of the organisational environment, human resource management policies and procedures, interpersonal relationships etc. which is tied with normative commitment (an employee ought to be in an organisation) and continuance commitment (an employee need to be in an organisation).

Freeman (1978) had observed more than twenty years ago and reported job satisfaction is a good predictor for job mobility over and above the effect of lagged wages. The more satisfied with their job people proclaim themselves, the less likely they are to quit. Recently, Clark, Georgellis and Sanfey (1998) expanded Freeman's model, using subjective evaluations of job satisfaction from German workers, to predict their mobility. The less likeliness of employees to quite their organisations is tied to continuance commitment which refers to the commitment that is based on the cost that is associated with leaving a specific organisation.

The potential cost of leaving an organisation includes threats of wasting time and effort spent acquiring non-transferable skills, losing attractive benefits, giving up seniority based privileges or having to uproot family, disrupt personal relationship and the lack of alternative wages if current one is lost.

Normative commitment refers to the employee's perceived obligation to remain with their organisation or reflect the feeling of obligation to continue employment in an organisation. Wiener (1982) suggested that the feeling of obligation to remain with an organisation might result from internalisation or normative pressure exerted on an individual prior entry into the organisation (family, cultural orientation) or following entry (organisational orientation). Normative commitment might also develop when an organisation provides the employee with "reward in advance" (paying college tuition) or incur significant cost in proving employment (cost associated with job training). For example, one can feel loyal to a family business or indebted to an organisation because it has paid for one's education. Once an employee is satisfied with his training process, pay package and socialisation process the employee feels a sense of obligation towards the organisation and stay in the organisation because the organisation has done a lot to him. An example could be that an organisation can spend enough money to train an employee in a life time profession. Satisfied, this employee may decide to be committed to the organisation for a period of time to compensate the organisation with his services for what they did to him.

It has been suggested that self-actualisation in the workplace can only be accomplished through the creation of opportunities for employee promotion (Ting, 1997). This view is supported by Ellickson and Logsdon (2002) who concluded that satisfaction with promotional opportunities is positively and significantly related to the job satisfaction of municipal workers. A number of scholars (McCausland, Pouliakas & Theodossiou, 2005; Saari & Judge, 2004) suggest that there is a direct and positive association between promotional opportunities and job satisfaction. When employees perceive that there are high chances for promotion, they feel motivated to work harder to achieve organisational goals with a view to attaining elevated job designations and higher ranks (Dessler, 2008). By contrast, employees who are dissatisfied with the available promotional opportunities in their organisation usually demonstrate a greater intention to leave the organisation (Shields & Ward, 2001) which can be tied with the quite intentions attached to continuance commitment when there is lack of opportunities or benefits in an organisation.

Job satisfaction is a result of an individual's perception and evaluation of their job influenced by their own unique needs, values and expectations, which they regard as being important to them (Sempene et al., 2002). Research has indicated that job satisfaction does not come about in isolation, as it is dependent on organisational variables such as structure, size, pay, working conditions and leadership, which represent the organisational climate (Sempene et al., 2002). However, if job satisfaction is absent and other work opportunities present themselves, turnover could well increase (Martins & Coetzee 2007). Job satisfaction can be viewed as a reaction to a job, arising from what an individual seeks in a job in comparison with the actual outcomes that the job provides to the individual (Rothmann & Coetzer 2002). However continuance and normative commitments are gotten from the interaction between an organisation and its employees, just to say that these two construct of commitment does not come in isolation and is somehow tied to the pay and working condition factors of job satisfaction as stipulated by Sempene et al. (2002).

According to Ting (1997), remuneration has a significant influence on job satisfaction amongst government employees. Similarly, Robbins (2003) emphasises that equitable rewards, which refer to compensation systems that are perceived as fair and in line with employee expectations, are a strong determinant of job satisfaction. In another study conducted by Kebriael and Moteghedhi (2009), public employees attributed the dissatisfaction with their jobs to low benefits and salaries. Additionally, NaeemIlham, Hadi, Shishi & Piarala (2011) also found significant positive relationships between job satisfaction and remuneration amongst civil servants in the Republic of Maldives. This demonstrates that when employees perceive that their remuneration is fair, they are most likely to experience a feeling of satisfaction. This is because income helps individuals to meet certain universal needs and, therefore, income, at least at lower levels, is an antecedent to job satisfaction and subjective well-being. Continuance commitment refers to an awareness of the cost associated with leaving the organisation and it indicates that an employee will remain in an organisation because of the financial reward he/she gets from the organisation, once this is absent the employee starts looking for an alternative job or if the employee is not satisfied with the reward he/she will show a lower degree of continuance commitment.

This study will be peculiar because little research has been done in the area of SMEs in Cameroon patterning to job satisfaction and commitment. Basically, this work will bring out the situation of employees of SMEs in Cameroon as per how they are satisfied to their job and

how this satisfaction will make them to be committed to their jobs. This study will widen the understanding of owners of SMEs as per the concepts discussed

2. Problem statement

Williams (1986) recognised an improvement in satisfaction to be effective to develop organisational commitment. Job satisfaction, means human positive view toward his/her job which results from some factors such as workplace conditions, type of management and salary (Shafie Abadi, 2005). Job satisfaction involves different aspects which are seen as determinant variables in commitment including professional dependence that affects workers satisfaction and interest of their job (Roohi, 2011). Organisational commitment is a force which binds workers to actions according to one or numerous goal(s) of their organisation (Vitell & Singapakdi, 2008). It is not to be doubted that job satisfaction of employees is very important. Managers need to concern the job satisfaction of their employees according to these three reasons: 1) there are proves showing that employees that are dissatisfied resign more 2) it is proven that satisfied employees enjoy better health and live longer 3) job satisfaction is a phenomenon which goes beyond the board an enterprise and its effects appears in the private life of the employees and out of their enterprise (Robins, 1970). It is from this background that we ought to bring out the influence of job satisfaction on the commitment of employees for their organisation. From this problem of statement the main research question is ‘what is the of job satisfaction on the commitment of employees for their organisations. From this main research question we had the following sub research questions;

- Does job satisfaction have an influence on the affective commitment employees have for their organisation?
- Does job satisfaction have an influence on the normative commitment employees have for their organisation?
- Does job satisfaction have an influence on the continuance commitment employees have for their organisation?

The main objective of the study was to find out the influence of job satisfaction on the commitment of employees of SMEs in Cameroon for their organisations. From this main objective we had the following specific objectives:

- To bring out the influence of job satisfaction on the affective commitment of employees for their organisations.

- To determine the influence of job satisfaction on the normative commitment of employees for their organisations.
- To assess the influence of job satisfaction on the continuance commitment of employees for their organisations.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study area

Cameroon is a rapidly changing middle-income developing country located in Central Africa around the Gulf of Guinea. It sustains a microcosm of equatorial and tropical geographic spaces, resources and multi-ethnic human diversity that make it one of the most self-sufficient in food production in Africa. Development of the oil sector and progress in agriculture in the late 1970s and early 80s led to an extraordinary annual growth rate that placed the country among the twenty safest countries in the world for foreign investments (Ndongko, 1986). Unfortunately, a collapse in world market prices for major exports and failure of the structural adjustment programme (SAP) led to an economic crisis in the late 1980s that affected all parts of the country (DeLancey and Mokeba, 1990). Despite high external debts, insecurity, unemployment and corruption, massive structural reforms by the government in the early 1990s have stimulated domestic economic activity; increased literacy rates and promote private sector activities (EIU, 2003).

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in Cameroon (SMEs) make up the bulk of enterprises in the country. According to the ministry of small and medium sized enterprises, social economy and artisanal (MINPMEESA) SMEs are defined into four categories which are; micro enterprises employing < 10 employees, small enterprises employing between 10 and 30 employees, medium enterprises employing between 30 to 50 employees and medium enterprises of superior level employing between 50 to 150 employees. The, Law N° 2010/010 of 13 April 2010 on the promotion of SMEs in Cameroon and other legal and institutional instruments paved the way for the sector with many such enterprises being created. With other accompanying measures for a level playing ground created, the SMEs, according to statistics from the Ministry of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, Social Economy and Handicraft (MINPMEESA), constitute 95 per cent of Cameroon's enterprises. The sectors concerned are; transformation, agriculture and animal husbandry, general commerce, construction and public works and most recently Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Going by the Research and Analysis Centre on the Economic and Social

Policies of Cameroon (CAMERCAP-PARC), 61,366 SMEs were created in Cameroon between 2010 and 2016, with 59,200 being local enterprises and 2,166 foreign.

In Cameroon, the majority of SMEs are situated in the towns of Douala, Yaounde, Bafoussam and Bamenda since this town have the majority of SMEs in Cameroon. Out of the 93 969 enterprises in Cameroon as per RGE (2009), 35.1% of these enterprises is found in Douala, 23.9% in Yaoundé, 8.9% in Bafoussam and 6.9% in Bamenda.

3.2 Description of data

Our sample size was based on employees of small and medium size enterprises (SMEs) in the respective towns stated above and our research was limited to the field of motivation, job satisfaction and commitment.

The methodology of this research combines primary and secondary data collection. The primary data will be collected using organisational commitment questionnaire of Allen and Meyer (1990) which comprises of affective commitment questionnaire, continuance commitment questionnaire and normative commitment questionnaire. For what concerns job satisfaction, we will use the job satisfaction questionnaire devised by Balçı (1985). These questionnaires was adapter to the context of our study and questions in the questionnaire were scaled according to likert scale as (1) strongly disagree (2) disagree (3) neither agree nor disagree (4) agree (5) strongly agree.

Out of the 1900 questionnaire administer, 1556 were judged to be exploitable making a rate of 81.89%. The majority of the rejected questionnaires were those that all the items were not filled.

The majority of the employees of the sample are male or men representing 52.8% of our sample while the remaining 47.2% are women making a total of 725 employees of our sample being women. The bulk of the respondent of the sample belong to the age group 25-34 making a sum of 754 respondents that is 48.5%, next by 18-24 with a total of 415 and 296 respondents between 35-44 years, followed by 80 respondents for the age group 45-59 years and lastly 11 respondents were of the age ≥ 60 . Pertaining to marital status, the majority of the respondents are single or not married representing 57.4% that is 893 respondents, followed by 629 respondents who are married.

3.3 Estimation framework

From the review of literature bringing in relation the concepts of the study and from the stated objectives above an estimated framework for the study was developed as thus:

Figure N°1: Estimated framework

Source: Author

From the framework, three hypotheses were formulated as per the relations between job satisfaction and commitment brought out by the theories consulted in the literature review.

H₁: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the affective commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisations.

H₂: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the normative commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisation.

H₃: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the continuance commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisation.

The hypotheses of the study were tested using Pearson correlation and reinforced with simple regression analyses.

4. Presentation and Discussion of Results

The results will be presented as per the objectives of the study. This will be done by bringing out the results gotten from Pearson moment correlation and simple regression analyses respectively

4.1 Effect of job satisfaction on Affective commitment

The influence of job satisfaction on affective commitment is presented based on hypothesis H₁: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the affective commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisations. The table below represent the relation using Pearson correlation test.

Table N°1: Relation between job satisfaction and affective commitment

		Affective commitment	Job satisfaction
Affective commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	0.564**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	1556	1556
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.564**	1

Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	1556	1556

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Our data

From **table N°1**, it can be seen that there is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment at a significant level of 1% and with a correlation coefficient of 0.564. This implies that with an increase in employees' satisfaction level the affective commitment employees have for their organisation may also increase. From the table above we can accept hypotheses H_1 : *Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the affective commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisations*. This result is in line with the results of Khan et al (2011) which indicated that job satisfaction had a significant and positive relationship with organisational commitment with a correlation coefficient of 0.494, though not directly related to affective commitment. Affective commitment is a subset of organisational commitment. Tang and LiPing (1999) report that a relationship exists between job satisfaction and organisational commitment, and Woer (1998) found that organisational commitment relates to job satisfaction, which both support this result. The result of regression analyses is presented on the tables below, based on the simple regression

Table N° 2: Showing Model Summaryb of AC and JS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.612a	.375	.374	4.03648

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: affective commitment

Source: Our data

Table N° 3: Showing ANOVAa of AC on JS

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15145.460	2	7572.730	464.780	.000b
	Residual	25270.702	1551	16.293		
	Total	40416.162	1553			

a. Dependent Variable: affective commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

Source: Our data

Table N°4: Showing regression coefficientsa of AC on IM and JS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	10.136	.496		20.426	.000
Job satisfaction	.320	.024	.358	13.416	.000

a. Dependent Variable: affective commitment

Source: Our data

From table 2 it is seen that R2 is 0.375, which means that job satisfaction and intrinsic motivation explains affective commitment by 37.5%. This signifies that the dependent variable is been explained by the independent variables at 37.5% at a significant level of 1% and F=464.780 as seen in table 3.

From the regression coefficients in table 4, the intercept 10.136 (constant) represents the estimated value of affective commitment job satisfaction are zero. The slop of job satisfaction 0.320 means change in affective commitment of 0.320 when job satisfaction increases by 1. Thus, factors of job satisfaction are most effective in predicting the affective commitment of employees for their organisation. Thus job satisfaction has an influence on the affective commitment of employees for their organization. Then, the prediction model can be demonstrated as follows:

Equation 1..... AC= 10.136 + 0.320β1

The results obtained from simple regression are same with that from Pearson correlation showing a positive relationship between the dependent and the independent variable. From the above regression coefficients in table 4, we can accept hypothesis H1 as done in the Pearson correlation analyses in table 1 above.

Our results are in conformity with those of Lumley, Coetzee, Tladinyane & Ferreira (2011) and Bilgin & Demirer (2012) who also reported a positive significant relationship between job satisfaction and affective commitment.

4.2 Effect of job satisfaction on normative commitment

Here we are going to bring out the relation between job satisfaction and normative commitment using person correlation as well as regression analyses. For this link to be put to light we formulated hypotheses H2: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the

normative commitment of employees for their organisation. This relation is shown in the table below using Pearson correlation analyses;

Table N°5: Relation between job satisfaction and normative commitment

		Normative commitment	Job satisfaction
Normative commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	0.561**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	1556	1556
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.561**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	1556	1556

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Our data

Table 5 shows that there is a strong and positive relation between job satisfaction and normative commitment with a significant level of 1% and with a correlation coefficient of 0.561. From the above table, hypothesis H2: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the normative commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisation is accepted.

Our result is similar to that of Ian Howard Frederick Bull (2005) who found out that there was a significant and positive relation between job satisfaction and normative commitment of high school teachers of disadvantageous areas in Western Cape Town (South Africa) at a significant level of 1% with a correlation coefficient of 0.406.

The results of regression analyses as stated by hypotheses two is presented in the tables below

Table N°6: Showing Model Summaryb of NC on JS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	.582a	.339	.338	3.71927

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: normative commitment

Source: Our data

Table 7: Showing ANOVAa of NC on JS

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	11006.964	2	5503.482	397.852	.000b
Residual	21482.627	1553	13.833		
Total	32489.591	1555			

a. Dependent Variable: normative commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

Source: Our data

Table 8: Showing regression Coefficientsa of NC on JS

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	8.713	.399		21.832	.000
Job satisfaction	.343	.022	.428	15.832	.000

a. Dependent Variable: normative commitment

Source: Our data

Table 6 above show that R² is 0.339, which means that job satisfaction explains normative commitment by 33.9%. This signifies that the dependent variable is been explained by the independent variables at 33.9% at a significant level of 1% and F=397.852 as seen in table 7. From the regression coefficients in table 8, the intercept 8.713 (constant) represents the estimated value of normative commitment when job satisfaction is zero. The slop of job satisfaction 0.343 means change in normative commitment of 0.343 when job satisfaction increases by 1. This implies that factors of job satisfaction are predictors of the normative commitment of employees for their organisation. Thus job satisfaction has an influence on the normative commitment of employees for their organization. Then, the prediction model can be demonstrated as follows:

Equation 2..... NC= 8.713 + 0.3430β1

The results obtained from the regression analyses in table 8 are same as those obtained from the correlation analyses in table 5 above showing a positive relation between the dependent and independent variables, thus hypotheses H2 is accepted as in the case of correlation analyses.

Our results are in line with that of Muhammad et al. (2019), who did a study on the nexus of employee's commitment, job satisfaction, and job performance: An analysis of FMCG industries of Pakistan. Their results showed that there exist a positive impact of normative organizational commitment on employee's job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.31$, C.R (t-value) = 2.458, p-values = 0.000). Our results are different from that of Ismail (2012), who carried out a study on organizational commitment and job satisfaction among staff of higher learning education institutions in Kelantan and realised that there was no significant relationship between normative commitment and job satisfaction.

4.3 Effect of job satisfaction on continuance commitment

For this relation to be put in place, a hypothesis was formulated based on the literature, which is H₃: Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the continuance commitment of employees for their organisation.

Table N°9: Relation between job satisfaction and continuance commitment

		Continuance commitment	Job satisfaction
Continuance Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	0.525**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	1556	1556
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	0.525**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	1556	1556

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Our data

From **table 9**, it can be seen that there is a strong positive relation between job satisfaction and continuance commitment at a significant level of 1% and with a correlation coefficient of

0.525 and both variables move in the same direction. This is to say that an increase in job satisfaction may lead to an increase in continuance commitment. From the above analyses hypotheses H_3 : *Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the continuance commitment of employees of SMEs for their organisation* was accepted

Our study is in line with that of Ian Howard Frederick Bull (2005) which indicates that there is a moderate relationship between normative commitment and job satisfaction amongst the sample of teachers from disadvantaged schools in the Western Cape (South Africa) at a significant level of 1% with a correlation coefficient of 0.406.

The results of regression analyses as stated by hypotheses two is presented in the tables below

Table N°10: Showing Model Summary^b of CC on JS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.558 ^a	.312	.311		3.39359

a. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

b. Dependent Variable: continuance commitment

Source: Our data

Table 11: Showing ANOVA^a of CC on JS

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	8093.965	2	4046.983	351.409	.000 ^b
Residual	17885.034	1553	11.516		
Total	25978.999	1555			

a. Dependent Variable: continuance commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), job satisfaction

Source: Our data.

Table N°12: Showing regression Coefficients^a of CC on JS

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.629	.364		15.458	.000
Job satisfaction	.261	.020	.365	13.215	.000

a. Dependent Variable: total of continuance commitment

Source: Our data

R^2 is 0.312 as seen in **table 10** implies that job satisfaction explains continuance commitment by 31.2%. This signifies that the dependent variable is been explained by the independent variables at 31.2% at a significant level of 1% and $F=351.409$ as seen in table 11.

The regression coefficients in table 12 show that the intercept 5.629 (constant) which represents the estimated value of continuance commitment when job satisfaction are zero. The slop of job satisfaction 0.261 means change in continuance commitment of 0.261 when job satisfaction increases by 1. Thus, factors of job satisfaction are most effective in predicting the continuance commitment of employees for their organization. Thus job satisfaction has an influence on the continuance commitment of employees for their organization. Then, the prediction model can be demonstrated as follows:

Equation 3.....
$$CC = 5.629 + 0.261\beta_1$$

From the above analyses in table 12 we realize that our results are same with that obtained from correlation analyses in table 9, thus hypotheses H_2 is accepted as was done in the case of correlation analyses. So we can conclude that using both Pearson correlation analyses and multiple regression analyses we had the same results.

Our results are in line with that of Kumar & Kumar (2016) who carried out a research on job satisfaction and organisational commitment in the hospitality industry: an empirical study and found out that job satisfaction had a positive and significant influence on the continuance commitment of employees.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

This study was based on the influence of job satisfaction on the commitment of employees of SMEs of Cameroon for their organization. For this objective to be met, data was collected using questionnaire on a sample size of 1556 employees of SMEs in Cameroon. The relation between the two variables (job satisfaction and commitment) was brought out through Pearson correlation and regression analyses. The result of the study reveals that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the affective, normative and continuance commitment.

The result shows that job satisfaction is an important indicator and determinant of the commitment of employees of SMEs in Cameroon for their organization. The results discussed above reveals that job satisfaction has a stronger influence on normative commitment than affective commitment, followed by continuance commitment. This is shown by the slope of job satisfaction of 0.343 meaning change in normative commitment of 0.343 when job satisfaction increases by 1, with R^2 value 0.338 (results obtained from regression analyses).

On the other hand results obtained from Pearson correlation shows that job satisfaction has a stronger relation on affective commitment followed by normative commitment and continuance commitment respectively. This is shown by the positive significant influence of job satisfaction on the affective commitment of employees with $r=0.564$ and at a significant level of 1%.

Though we have taken all possible steps to provide the result in a holistic way but as a natural phenomenon of any research, our study is also not free from some limitations. It cannot be said that this study touched all the aspects of job satisfaction and commitment. We applied our study only on SMEs of 4 major towns in Cameroon; meanwhile a sample of all the national territory could give supplementary information. Some openings for future research could be by adding some other variables of job satisfaction other than what we used. Or still the concept of satisfaction could be seen in two perspectives; intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction, and then explore the relation with the different foci of commitment,

Based on the results obtained the following policy recommendation could be made to increase the commitment levels of employees of SMEs in Cameroon for their organisations;

- The management of SMEs have to put more efforts to ameliorate the job satisfaction of their employees. Since job satisfaction has a strong influence on normative commitment, elements of satisfaction such as advance payment, good medical attention and good salaries should be instituted in SMEs so that it will post the satisfaction of the employees to their job.
- The management of SMEs should recruit employees based on their job fit with the vacant position, since it is show by this study that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on affective commitment. When employees love their job and their job fits with their knowhow, they must obviously be satisfied and thus committed to their organisation.

Generally the management of SMEs should elaborate strategies to constantly increase the satisfaction of their employees to their job as to keep these employees committed to their job as shown by the results of this study.

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